

TERPENE COMPOUNDS. PART I SYNTHETIC STUDY ON THE STRUCTURE OF AZULENE.

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Two structural formulæ (I) and (II) have been suggested for the blue pigment which is associated with the high boiling fractions of certain volatile oils (Kremers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45** 717; Ruzicka and Rudolf, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1926, **9**, 118; Ruzicka and van Veen, *Annalen*, **476**, 70; Ruzicka and Haagen-Smit, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, **14**, 1929, 1104; Birrel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1248; 1935, **57**, 883; Melville, *ibid.*, 1933, **55**, 3288; Birrel, *ibid.*, 1935, **57**, 893). The structure (I) was advocated by Kremers (*loc. cit.*) and (II) by Ruzicka and Haagen-Smit (*loc. cit.*) as explaining many known facts concerning the substance.

Preliminary experiments which have been carried out in this direction with the object of synthesising (I) are now described.

Ethyl Δ^1 -tetrahydrobenzoate is condensed with ethyl sodio-cyanoacetate, and the resulting sodio derivative is allowed to react with ethyl bromoacetate, when ethyl 1-carbethoxycyclohexane-2- α -cyanosuccinate (III) is obtained (*cf.* Bardhan and Chatterjee, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 479). This on hydrolysis gives 1-carboxycyclohexane-2-succinic acid (IV). The ethyl ester of the above acid is cyclised with granulated sodium to yield ethyl (o:3:4-bicyclo)-nonan-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate (V). This on hydrolysis gives the required (o:3:4-bicyclo)-nonan-2-one-4-carboxylic acid (VI). The corresponding keto-ester is treated with methyl magnesium iodide to yield a neutral product (VII), which on dehydrogenation with selenium probably furnishes (VIII).

Experiments on similar lines are in progress with *p*-methylcyclohexanone for the synthesis of the compound (I) given above.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl Δ^1 -tetrahydrobenzoate was prepared according to the following method in good yield. *cyclo*Hexanone (100 g.) was shaken with a solution of sodium bisulphite (200 g.) in water (250 c.c.) and the mixture was cooled in ice and gradually treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (80 g.) in water (150 c.c.). After 2 hours the cyanohydrin was extracted with ether, washed with water and then with a saturated solution of sodium chloride, dried (anhydrous sodium sulphate), and the solvent removed with the addition of 2 drops of concentrated sulphuric acid. The crude cyanohydrin was refluxed with 5-6 volumes of concentrated hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.19) for 7 hours on the steam-bath and the hydroxy-acid extracted with ether, yield 105 g. The hydroxy-acid (50 g.) was treated with phosphorus pentachloride (140 g.) and heated on the water-bath for about 12 hours. The reaction product was cooled, poured into ice-cold absolute alcohol (200 c.c.) and left overnight. It was then diluted with water and the chloro-ester (100 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (100 g. in 300 c.c. of alcohol) for about 2 hours on the water-bath. After dilution, alcohol was removed on the water-bath as completely as possible, the brown solution cooled, filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid, and the product collected in ether, dried and ether removed; yield 35 g. *Ethyl* Δ^1 -tetrahydrobenzoate was prepared by a refluxing a mixture of the acid (161 g.), absolute alcohol (400 c.c.) and concentrated H_2SO_4 (61 c.c.) for 6 hours, b.p. $96^\circ/10$ mm., yield 165 g.

Ethyl 1-Carboethoxycyclohexane-2- α -cyanosuccinate (III).—A solution of sodium (4.6 g.) in absolute alcohol (75 c.c.) was cooled in ice and gradually mixed with ethyl cyanoacetate (22.6 g.). After half an hour ethyl Δ^1 -tetrahydrobenzoate (33.6 g.) was added, and the mixture refluxed on the steam-bath for 24 hours. The brownish crystalline mass, consisting of the

sodio-derivative of the condensation product, was cooled in ice and treated with ethyl bromoacetate (33.6 g.), the mixture being finally heated for 6 hours. After cooling, the product was poured into water, and the oil extracted with ether, washed, dried, and fractionated under reduced pressure. Ethyl 1-carbethoxycyclohexane-2- α -cyanosuccinate had b. p. 204-206°/4 mm., yield 45 g. (Found: C, 61.1; H, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{27}O_6N$ requires C, 61.1; H, 7.6 per cent).

Ethyl 1-Carboxycyclohexane-2-succinate (IV).—A solution of the above cyano-ester (III, 40 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (45 c.c.) was diluted with water (320 c.c.) and refluxed for 50 hours on a sand-bath. Practically the whole of the acid went into solution. After cooling, the mixture was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The gummy acid (30 g.) obtained was converted by the alcohol vapour method into ethyl 1-carboxycyclohexane-2-succinate, a colourless limpid oil, b. p. 177°-185°/7 mm., yield 25 g. (in a typical experiment 65 g. of acid, 120 c.c. of absolute alcohol, 12 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid were treated and 3 litres of alcohol vapourised for 4 hours). (Found: C, 62.5; H, 8.5. $C_{17}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 62.1; H, 8.53 per cent).

Ethyl (0:3:4-bicyclo)-Nonan-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate (V).—The above ester (IV, 8 g.) was heated with granulated sodium (1.2 g.) and benzene (25 c.c.) until the whole of the sodium disappeared (2 hours). After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried, and evaporated. The residue gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 188°/8mm., yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 63.4; H, 8.0. $C_{15}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 63.8; H, 7.8 per cent).

(0:3:4-bicyclo)-Nonan-2-one-4-carboxylic Acid (VI).—The product (28 g.) was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours; the cooled solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether and the extract washed with water. On removing ether the keto-acid crystallises, m.p. 136°, yield 18 g. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 7.6. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.6 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 220°. (Found: N, 17.2. $C_{11}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires N, 17.5 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by refluxing a solution of the keto-acid (VI, 18 g.) in absolute alcohol (68 c.c.), saturated at 0° with hydrochloric acid gas and working up the product in the usual manner, b.p. 143-44°/8mm. (Found: C, 68.5; H, 8.4. $C_{12}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 68.5; H, 8.5 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 159°. (Found: N, 15.6. $C_{13}H_{21}O_3N_3$ requires N, 15.7 per cent).

Ethyl 3-Methyl-(0:3:4-bicyclo)-nonan-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate.—The ester of the compound (IV) (8 g.) was cyclised with sodium (1.2 g.) in benzene. The product was cooled in ice and gradually treated with excess of methyl iodide and the whole warmed until neutral. The mixture was treated with cold water and the benzene layer separated, dried and distilled, ethyl 3-methyl-(0:3:4-bicyclo)-nonan-2-one-3:4-dicarboxylate being obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 174°/7mm., yield 4 g. It did not give a colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 8.1. $C_{16}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 64.8; H, 8.1 per cent).

Action of Methyl Magnesium Iodide on Ethyl (0:3:4-bicyclo)-nonan-2-one-4-carboxylate: Formation of Compound (VII).—The ester (10 g.), diluted with dry ether (10 c.c.), was slowly added to a solution of methyl magnesium iodide (prepared from 3.6 g. of magnesium in 100 c.c. of dry ether and 11 c.c. of methyl iodide) cooled in ice-water. After standing for 12 hours at the ordinary temperature the product was decomposed with ice and dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was extracted ten times with ether and the extract was washed with water, dried and evaporated. The brown residue was boiled with a solution of potassium hydroxide (10 g.) in water (10 c.c.) and alcohol (90 c.c.) for 1 hour; the alcohol was removed as completely as possible and the residue diluted with water and repeatedly extracted with ether, yield 4 g. The neutral product thus obtained exhibits bluish fluorescence in ethereal solution, b.p. 154°/4mm. (Found: C, 74.4; H, 10.7. $C_{13}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 73.6; H, 11.3 per cent).

1-isoPropylidene-3-methylindene (VIII).—The neutral product (VII) was heated with selenium at 300-320° for about 29 hours. The product (probably a mixture) was extracted with ether and after removing the solvent fractionated and a small quantity of a substance at 145-48°/11 mm. was collected and crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 49°. (Found: C, 90.5; H, 8.0. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{14}$: C, 91.7; H, 8.2 per cent).

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